

Clinical Trial Details (PDF Generation Date :- Sun, 09 Jul 2023 04:03:22 GMT)

CTRI Number	CTRI/2022/03/041355 [Registered on: 24/03/2022] - Trial Registered Prospectively	
Last Modified On	17/02/2023	
Post Graduate Thesis	Yes	
Type of Trial	Interventional	
Type of Study	Process of Care Changes Behavioral Other (Specify) [Play Therapy]	
Study Design	Randomized, Parallel Group Trial	
Public Title of Study	Play Therapy for Improving the Early Childhood Development Parameters of Hospitalized Rural Children	
Scientific Title of Study	Effectiveness of Play Therapy Programme in Promoting Early Child Development of under-5 Children visiting Tertiary Care Hospital in Rural Settings: A Randomized Controlled Trial.	
Secondary IDs if Any	Secondary ID	Identifier
	NIL	NIL
Details of Principal Investigator or overall Trial Coordinator (multi-center study)	Details of Principal Investigator	
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	Designation	Research Consultant and PhD Scholar
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Source of Monetary or Material Support	Source of Monetary or Material Support			
	> Datta Meghe Institute of Medical Sciences, Wardha			
Primary Sponsor	Primary Sponsor Details			
Name	Manoj Patil			
Address	Research House , JNMC Campus, Datta Meghe Institute of Medical Sciences, Wardha			
Type of Sponsor	Other [Self]			
Details of Secondary Sponsor	Name	Address		
	NIL	NIL		
Countries of Recruitment	List of Countries			
	India			
Sites of Study	Name of Principal Investigator	Name of Site	Site Address	Phone/Fax/Email
	Manoj Patil	Acharya Vinoba Bhawe Rural Hospital, Sawangi (M)	Department of Paediatrics, Datta Meghe Institute of Medical Sciences, Wardha Wardha MAHARASHTRA	9049167076 mpatil98dent@gmail.com
Details of Ethics Committee	Name of Committee	Approval Status	Date of Approval	Is Independent Ethics Committee?
	Institutional Ethics Committee, Datta Meghe Institute of Medical Sciences University	Approved	29/01/2021	No
Regulatory Clearance Status from DCGI	Status	Date		
	Not Applicable	No Date Specified		
Health Condition / Problems Studied	Health Type	Condition		
	Patients	Other specified health status		
Intervention / Comparator Agent	Type	Name	Details	
	Intervention	Play Therapy Sessions	Structured Play Therapy Sessions of 45 minutes will be delivered to Intervention Group during hospital stay and at home visits during follow-up till 1 year from enrollment.	
	Comparator Agent	Routine Hospital Care	The control group will receive routine hospital care but Not the Play Therapy sessions as that with Intervention group.	
Inclusion Criteria	Inclusion Criteria			

	Age From	6.00 Month(s)
	Age To	4.00 Year(s)
	Gender	Both
	Details	1. Children admitted to Pediatric Ward of AVBRH aged 6 months to 4 years. 2. Children from villages within 25 Km periphery of AVBRH. 3. Parents consenting for Participation of Child in Play Therapy Programme.
Exclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria	
	Details	1. Seriously sick, Moribund children with life threatening conditions. 2. Children in Intensive Care treatment.
Method of Generating Random Sequence	Permuted block randomization, variable	
Method of Concealment	Alternation	
Blinding/Masking	Not Applicable	
Primary Outcome	Outcome	Timepoints
	Improvements in Early Child Development parameters by 0.5 SD in intervention compared to Control arm.	At 12 months from the date of enrolment
Secondary Outcome	Outcome	Timepoints
	A dedicated Play Therapy Kit specially designed for hospitalized children, with provision of follow-up and assessment mechanisms through online mode.	2 years from the start of trial.
Target Sample Size	Total Sample Size=200 Sample Size from India=200 Final Enrollment numbers achieved (Total)=Applicable only for Completed/Terminated trials Final Enrollment numbers achieved (India)=Applicable only for Completed/Terminated trials	
Phase of Trial	N/A	
Date of First Enrollment (India)	01/04/2022	
Date of First Enrollment (Global)	No Date Specified	
Estimated Duration of Trial	Years=1 Months=6 Days=0	
Recruitment Status of Trial (Global)	Not Yet Recruiting	
Recruitment Status of Trial (India)	Open to Recruitment	
Publication Details	Plan to publish in Pubmed/Scopus/Web of Science Indexed journals.	
Brief Summary	<p>Early childhood is a period of rapid development. Play and recreation is naturally an essential part of childhood and is vital to normal development. Through various types of play and recreational activities, children start to learn, try to express themselves, cope with anxiety, develop their skills and master the experiences. Play can also help to facilitate in learning how to adapt and tolerate the healthcare and hospitalization experience. This trial aims to study the effectiveness of a structured 'Play Therapy Programme' in improving the child development parameters of under-5 children</p>	

hospitalized at Acharya Vinoba Bhave Rural Hospital, Wardha.

Primary Objectives:

1. To develop a structured 'Play Therapy Programme' for the parents and children under-5 years visiting the paediatric inpatient facility of AVBRH.
2. To enhance knowledge and skills of parents on early child development and improve parent-child interactions.
3. To improve the Motor, Language, Cognitive and Social-emotional development parameters of under-5 children visiting AVBRH, through play therapy and follow-up at scheduled home visits.

All participants consenting for the participation in study will be assigned the Unique ID. Using blocked randomization process(45) with age groups as Blocking variable, participants will be allocated either to intervention or control groups. Age groups will be –

1. 6 months to 24 months,
2. 25 months to 48 months.

All children hospitalized in AVBRH, scheduled to have a stay of minimum 3 days in hospital and their parents signing the informed consent will be enrolled in the study.

the sample size required is **200 (100 per group)** with equal distribution into Intervention and Control Groups.

Duration of the Interventions:

1. All the children who fall in the age range of 6 months to four years old will receive intervention (along with their parents) every day during their hospital stay for one hour to 2 hours.
2. The children will receive fortnightly follow-up sessions through home visits (or through Social Media Group meetings if needed) till 12 months from enrolment in the programme.
3. Activities described in the Play Therapy Manual will be followed for the follow-up sessions at home visits.

For all children, changes will be observed in the-

1. Physical Development (Using Developmental Milestones Checklist-II)

a. Improvement in Fine Motor scores

b. Improvement in Gross Motor scores

2. Cognitive Development Scores (Using Developmental Milestones Checklist-II)

3. Language Development Scores(Using Developmental Milestones Checklist-II)

4. Socioemotional Development Scores(Using Profile of Socio-emotional Development)

5. Home Environment (Using HOME Inventory Assessment)

6. Parent-child Interactions (Using Observation of Mother Child Interaction Tool)

Outcomes: We expect improvements in Child Development Scores by 0.5 SD in intervention compared to control arm at the end of 1 year of intervention.